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List of abbreviations

AAR	Android Archive
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BART	Balloon Analogue Risk Task
BBI	Beat-to-Beat Interval
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graphs
dBM-DEV	Digital Biomarkers Development
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCP	Healthcare Professional
LEDD	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dosage
LLM	Large Language Model
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PGO	PostgreSQL Operator
RBD	REM sleep Behaviour Disorder
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

Executive summary

D4.4 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (MVP)' delivers the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) version of the AI-PROGNOSIS' three applications, i.e., mAI-Health, mAI-Care and mAI-Insights, which altogether form an ecosystem of digital health tools for supporting Parkinson's Disease (PD) screening, disease management and clinical decision-making on medication selection and anticipated response. Building on the alpha versions delivered in D4.2 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (Alpha version)' and the technical specifications refined in D4.3 'Updated technical specifications, architecture and product backlog', this deliverable describes the maturation of the ecosystem into functional MVPs ready for real-world proof-of-concept validation.

The transition from alpha to MVP was driven by updated user requirements and extensive co-creation activities with the patient panel and clinical partners, ensuring that both patient-facing and clinician-facing features are aligned with their needs and workflows. Most planned functionalities have now been implemented, including smartwatch data capturing, several self-reporting and self-logging assessments, the active cognitive and motor function tests, and initial feedback elements, such as digital biomarker graphs and clinician-facing reports on PD risk, progression, and medication response.

At the application level, the usage and components of the three applications are described, providing a clear overview of their functionality. The backend is underpinned by a robust, Kubernetes-based infrastructure that hosts data storage, analytics, and workflow orchestration. Apache Airflow coordinates the project's data processing pipelines, which analyse wearable and clinical data to generate digital biomarkers and predictions of PD risk, progression, and medication response. A Large Language Model (LLM)-based explainability module has been further set up to generate clinician-facing lay summaries of predictions and associated explainability evidence. Monitoring and deployment processes follow GitOps principles to ensure stability, traceability, and scalability.

Overall, D4.4 demonstrates that the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem has progressed from early prototypes to a coherent, integrated MVP towards supporting PD risk monitoring and patient management. The remaining product features and data processing pipeline refinements are underway and will be delivered with the final, refined MVPs as part of D4.5 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (refined MVP)'.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

D4.4 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (MVP)' is part of WP4, 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem' and is the product of tasks T4.2 'Application Design and Development', T4.3 'Data storage and analytics infrastructure', and T4.4 'System orchestration, verification and monitoring'. It serves as a companion report to the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) versions of the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem for Parkinson's disease screening and care, i.e., mAI-Health, mAI-Care and mAI-Insights applications.

This document describes a more matured version of the user-facing components established in D4.2 'The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (Alpha version)' and expands certain deployment specifications beyond those defined in D4.3 'Updated Technical Specifications, Architecture, and Product Backlog'. Furthermore, it will serve as the baseline for the refined MVPs delivered in D4.5 'The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (refined MVP)'.

1.2 Document structure

The document includes six sections, and it is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction to the present document.
- Section 2 describes the work done that led to the development of the MVPs.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the applications and the components they include.
- Section 4 gives a detailed description of the components.
- Section 5 describes the system's deployment specifications.
- Section 6 concludes with a summary of the next steps towards the refined MVPs.

The document also includes an Appendix with full screenshots of certain of mAI-Insights screens.

2 From alpha version to MVP

Following the development of the alpha versions of the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem's applications, a plan for transitioning to the MVPs was defined and executed. The transition from alpha to MVP versions required a systematic approach that incorporated feedback from the patient panel and clinicians, alongside input from technical partners, as well as insights gained from real-life app usage during the dBM-DEV study. The transition was guided by the updated user needs documented in D2.5 'Updated report on user research and co-creation' led by partner UU, which resulted into the refined functional and non-functional requirements reported in D4.3.

Building on these refinements, D4.3 also detailed the specific requirements for the predictive models' and digital biomarkers' input and data processing pipelines, ensuring alignment between clinical objectives and technical feasibility. With these specifications in place, application development progressed to incorporate and support those data processing pipelines, enabling the transition toward robust MVP-ready implementations.

The outputs generated through these pipelines, presented to HCPs via mAI-Insights, were subsequently validated through a series of co-creation sessions, ensuring their clinical relevance, clarity and usability. In parallel, patient-facing features, deployed in mAI-Health and

mAI-Care mobile applications underwent similar validation activities with the patient panel. This dual-track evaluation process ensured that both clinician and patient interfaces effectively supported real-world needs and aligned with the overarching goals of the AI-PRONGOSIS digital health ecosystem MVPs.

However, certain features are still work-in-progress and will be the subject of additional co-design sessions to ensure they fully align with the needs of the relevant stakeholders. These features are not critical for the initiation of the AI-PRA and AI-PMP clinical studies of the project, primarily aiming to validate the core functionalities of the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem, i.e., the accuracy of the underlying predictive models.

3 Container level

To ensure consistency with the structure of D4.3, the C4 model¹ is also utilised in this document, using the terms ‘containers’ for the applications and ‘components’ for pieces of code that cannot be independently deployed. The containers briefly described along all included components. **Table 1** summarises the user base of each container.

All mobile application containers are being developed in React Native using Expo², a TypeScript framework that enables flexible mobile application development using a wide range of open-source libraries. Parts of the application that need to interact with other packages, such as Garmin’s Health SDK, were developed using native code (specifically Kotlin programming language). The applications are available exclusively for Android.

Requirements for full usage of the mobile applications:

- A smartphone device with Android 11 or newer (API level 30).
- Minimum 250MB free storage for installation, with a recommended 3GB available for storage of collected data.
- A Garmin vívoactive 5 Smartwatch.
- An active Wi-Fi internet connection.

The mAI-Insights web application, designed for Healthcare Professionals (HCPs), was developed using Next.js³ with TypeScript, a React framework that enables developers to build fast, scalable and Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)-friendly web applications through features such as server-side rendering, static site generation, API routes and automatic code optimisation.

Requirements to access the mAI-Insights web application include:

- A device with internet connection (a computer or tablet is recommended for optimal user experience).
- A recent version of a modern web browser, such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or Safari.

Table 1 Userbase of mAI digital health ecosystem applications

Userbase	mAI-Health	mAI-Care	mAI-Insights
Persons without PD monitored for risk	✓		

¹ The C4 model: <https://c4model.com>

² Expo: <https://docs.expo.dev/>

³ Next.js: <https://nextjs.org/>

Persons with PD		✓	
Healthcare Professionals (primary and secondary care)			✓

3.1 mAI-Health container

The mAI-Health application is designed for persons without PD to help them monitor their PD risk status under the supervision of a primary or secondary HCP. The primary purpose is to collect data from the users that will be used by the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk prediction model, the output of which will be communicated and monitored by the attending HCP through the mAI-Insights web application. **Table 2** lists the components included in MVP of mAI-Health.

Table 2 List of components of the mAI-Health MVP

Component ID	Component name
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker
COMP-LDB	Smartphone local database
COMP-SRQ	Self-reporting assessments
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager

3.1.1 Installation and first usage

The application can be downloaded from the Google Play Store⁴. Once downloaded and installed, users need to either register for an account (this feature is not yet implemented) or log in (see **Figure 1**). Currently, log-in credentials are generated by partner INTRA, responsible for the data and user management infrastructure, and are available only for the AI-PRA study participants; a test user account is provided in Section 8 for demonstration purposes. After successful authentication, users are guided through the app onboarding process.

In the first step of onboarding, users are prompted to connect with their attending doctor. To do so, they must enter their doctor's code. A request is then sent to the doctor that has to accept it via the mAI-Insights web application. Once the request is completed, they are asked to provide personal details, specifically sex at birth, age, height, weight, bed and out-of-bed times. This information is also required for pairing and configuring the smartwatch. The out-of-bed time is also stored in the AI-PROGNOSIS backend, where it is used to schedule notifications regarding user actions.

The next steps of the onboarding (see **Figure 1**) include:

- Enabling notifications preferences
- Selecting the wrist on which the smartwatch will be worn
- Pairing the smartwatch with the smartphone
- Enabling data collection (see also Section 4.2)
- Inform users about how they can request help or send feedback; also provides access to the privacy policy and terms of use of the app

⁴ mAI-Health: <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.squaredev.maihealth2>

Figure 1 mAI-Health log-in and onboarding screens

3.1.2 Application navigation

The application’s navigation bar includes three tabs: the ‘Home screen’, ‘Learn’ and ‘Profile’ tab.

3.1.2.1 Home screen

On the home screen (see **Figure 2**), users can view the number of days monitored, the timestamp of the most recent smartwatch data upload, and their current and upcoming tasks.

Upon first log-in, users are prompted to complete a lifestyle and medical history profile through a self-reporting questionnaire listed under the ‘Current Tasks’. The task is active until it is completed (see Section 4.7). Once completed, it will reappear as a ‘Health update’ task after 6 months. The questionnaire includes questions about risk and prodromal markers of PD as defined by the Movement Disorders Society (Heinzel et al., 2019) that can be self-reported by the user. As part of the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment system, the questionnaire data will be combined with a PD risk score derived from smartwatch-based sleep and activity metrics to form an overall PD risk score/level.

Figure 2 mAI-Health 'Home screen'

Figure 3 mAI-Health 'Learn' tab

3.1.2.2 Learn

This section provides educational articles in lay language relevant to PD screening, with the first ones relating to the journey to a PD diagnosis and how technology, such as the one developed in AI-PROGNOSIS, can support the process (see **Figure 3**). This content is intended to improve the users' health literacy and help them create mental models of how the technology works to boost trust.

3.1.2.3 Profile

The profile tab consists of four different sub-sections, 'Account', 'Your doctor', 'Settings', and 'Support'. The application version is also displayed on this screen.

3.1.2.3.1 Account

In the Account subsection (see **Figure 4**), users can view and update the personal details they entered during onboarding (these are currently stored only on the user's device). They can also access the application's privacy policy and terms of use and log out.

3.1.2.3.2 Your doctor

In this sub-section, users have access to the details of their connected doctor (see **Figure 5**) and can switch to another doctor. Users are also informed that, based on mAI-Health data, risk reports are automatically generated and made available to the connected doctor.

Figure 4 mAI-Health 'Account' tab

Figure 5 mAI-Health 'Your doctor' tab

3.1.2.3.3 Settings

In Settings (see Figure 6), users can:

- Unpair the smartwatch
- Stop the data collection
- Enable/Disable task notifications
- Adjust the notifications time

3.1.2.3.4 Contact

Users can view the contact information of the clinical site through which they can request support (see Figure 7).

Figure 6 mAI-Health 'Settings' tab

Figure 7 mAI-Health 'Support' tab

3.1.3 Notifications

The mAI-Health application currently generates four types of user notifications (see also Section 4.9):

1. Data synchronisation (sync) notifications.
2. Bluetooth connection notifications.
3. Wi-Fi connection notifications.
4. Self-reporting task notifications.

3.2 mAI-Care container

The mAI-Care application is designed for individuals diagnosed with PD who want to track their symptoms with the support from their attending physician (secondary HCP). Patients will have access to tracked digital biomarkers of certain symptoms. In parallel, certain tracked data will serve as input to the AI-PROGNOSIS PD progression prediction model, the output of which will be communicated to the attending HCP via the mAI-Insights app. **Table 3** lists the components of the MVP of the mAI-Care app.

Table 3 List of components of the mAI-Care MVP

Component ID	Component name
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker
COMP-LDB	Smartphone local database
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard
COMP-ACT	Active cognition capturing (cognitive) tests
COMP-PAMT	Comprehensive motor function assessment test

COMP-SRQ	Self-reporting assessments
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager
COMP-VIS	Data visualisations

3.2.1 Installation and first usage

The installation, sign-in, and onboarding process are almost identical to the mAI-Health application (see Section 3.1.1).

3.2.2 Application navigation

The application’s navigation bar consists of four tabs: the ‘Home screen’, ‘Insights’, ‘Learn’, ‘Personal log’ and ‘Profile’ tabs.

3.2.2.1 Home screen

The home screen (see **Figure 8**) displays key monitoring information, including the total number of days the users have tracked their condition, the latest timestamp associated with data synchronised from their smartwatch, and a list of both current and upcoming tasks

At first login, the active cognitive and motor function assessment tests are listed under ‘Current tasks’, and users have five days to complete them, with the final deadline clearly indicated. Currently, as defined in the AI-PMP study protocol (evaluating the AI-PROGNOSIS prognostic and monitoring functionalities), these tests must be performed every two months, and they will be listed under ‘Upcoming tasks’ starting one week before they need to be performed.

Figure 8 mAI-Care ‘Home screen’

Figure 9 mAI-Care ‘Insights’ tab

Figure 10 mAI-Care 'Personal log' tab

3.2.2.2 Insights

Through this tab, users have access to tracked digital measurements of certain key PD symptoms (see **Figure 9** and Section 4.8). These measurements correspond to the digital biomarkers developed mainly in project tasks T3.1 ‘RBD and daytime somnolence tracking’ and T3.2 ‘Motor and cognitive function tracking’.

3.2.2.3 Personal log

In this section, users can self-log sleep problems that they have faced the previous night (see **Figure 10** and Section 4.7). In the refined MVP, users will be able to log activities of daily living that are affected by their condition and want to keep track of.

3.2.2.4 Learn

This section, like the one in mAI-Health (see Section 3.1.2.2), provides educational articles for individuals with PD, offering accessible information about life with PD and how technology can help with disease management (see **Figure 11**).

3.2.2.5 Profile

The profile tab consists of four different subsections: ‘Account’, ‘Your doctor’, ‘Settings’ and ‘Support’, same as mAI-Health (see Section 3.1.2.3). The only difference is that in the ‘Settings’ tab, users can check if the Research keyboard (see Section 4.4) is activated and set it up if not (see **Figure 12**). The Research keyboard provides the necessary input data for the measurement of digital biomarkers of slowness of fine movement (see project deliverable D3.3 ‘Final report on digital biomarkers for PD’).

Figure 11 mAI-Care ‘Learn’ tab

Figure 12 mAI-Care ‘Settings’ tab

3.2.3 Notifications

The mAI-Care application currently generates five types of user notifications (see Section 4.9):

1. Active test to-do notifications
2. Self-reporting task notifications
3. Data sync notifications

4. Bluetooth connection notifications
5. Wi-Fi connection notifications

3.3 mAI-Insights container

The mAI-Insights web application allows attending physicians to monitor and follow up on patients with PD and patients at risk, with the help of data collected via mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications, as well as receive reports on risk and progression estimations. It also allows access to the AI-assisted Medication Decision support (AIMED) module powered by the medication response predictive model AI-PROGNOSIS has developed. The latter allows the physician to input PD medication regimens and receive predictions of key adverse effects for a particular patient. Physicians are also able to input and keep a record of clinical data for their patients, certain of which also serve as input to the predictive models (see Section 2.3.12 in D4.3).

3.3.1 Access, first usage and app overview

The application is accessible via any internet-connected computer through a secure web-based interface. Users must complete authentication to access the system. Upon successful login, they are directed to the home screen (main dashboard).

3.3.1.1 Home screen

From the home screen (see **Figure 13**), users can view a comprehensive overview of all patients under their attendance, alongside a list of pending connection requests. To begin attending a patient, users must first establish a connection. Patients initiate this process through the mAI-Health and mAI-care applications (see Sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.1). HCPs can then review and choose to accept or reject these connection requests (see **Figure 14**). Once a connection is established, HCPs gain the ability to input clinical data and access the system's predictive outputs, including PD risk estimations and progression monitoring results.

Figure 13 mAI-Insights home screen

USER ID	REQUESTED ON	ACTIONS
maicare-user	11/12/2025	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 14 Connection requests in mAI-Insights

3.3.1.2 User profile

By navigating to the 'Profile' tab, physicians can view and update their personal information and account settings.

Profile
Dr. John Smith
 Neurology
 ID: mai-insights-user

Personal Information

First Name Dr. John	Last Name Smith
Email john.smith@hospital.com	Phone +1 (555) 123-4567
Specialization Neurology	Address 123 Medical Center Dr, Health City, HC 12345

Figure 15 Physician profile page in mAI-Insights

3.3.1.3 Patient list

The patient list is divided in two tabbed categories: 'Patients at risk' and 'Patients with Parkinson's Disease' (see **Figure 13**). Each table displays essential patient information in an easy-to-scan format, including user ID, name, age, sex and current risk level or PD stage.

3.3.1.4 Patient details

The patient details section offers a unified overview of all relevant patient information, an insights section, allows HCPs to input clinical data and access various analytical insights generated by the AI-PROGNOSIS system (see **Figure 16**).

Figure 16 Patient details page in mAI-Insights

This screen also includes an option for the HCP to remove their connection with the patient, if desired.

3.3.2 Parkinson's disease (PD) screening

The 'Insights' section, when accessed from the details page of a patient at risk, is the place where HCPs can input/access clinical data, alongside automatically generated PD risk reports. This section provides access to two areas (see **Figure 16**):

- Clinical consultations: Enables HCPs to input data from a new clinical consultation or review past clinical consultation data.
- Risk reports: Automatically-generated reports on PD risk estimated by the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment system.

3.3.2.1 Clinical consultations

During a clinical consultation, the HCPs are able to validate the risk and prodromal markers reported by their patient through the self-reporting questionnaire in mAI-Health and also input additional clinical data that can serve as input to the PD risk assessment system, such as a Polygenic Risk Score (see **Figure 17** and Appendix – mAI-Insights screens).

New clinical consultation
Review and update the status of each prodromal marker for the patient.

Sarah Mitchell
Age: 68 | Sex: F | Date of Birth: 30 / 4 / 1956

Risk/prodromal marker	LR+	LR-	Review by HCP	Reported by patient via mAI-Health
Male sex	1.2	0.8	Confirmed	Female
Regular pesticide exposure	1.5	NA	Suspected	No
Occupational solvent exposure	1.5	NA	Unknown	-
Non-use of caffeine	1.35	0.88	Confirmed	No
Former smoker	NA	0.91	Not present	Yes
Never smoker	1.2	NA	Not present	No

Figure 17 New clinical consultation page for patients at risk in mAI-Insights

3.3.2.2 PD risk report

The PD risk report is a structured report on the patient’s PD risk alongside explainability evidence, produced by the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment system (see Section 2.3.12.1 in D4.3 and Appendix – mAI-Insights screens).

The report first includes an AI-generated summary of the key findings (see Figure 18 and Section 5.4) in plain language, highlighting key risk contributors.

Name
Sarah Mitchell

Age: 68 | Sex: F | Date of birth: 30 / 4 / 1956 | BMI: 25.4 | Date of report: 12 Jun 2025 | Reporting period: Jan 2025 - Jun 2025

AI generated summary

The patient's overall Parkinson's Disease risk assessment for the period Jan 2025-Jun 2025 indicates a 75% probability of having Parkinson's, driven by a very high digital risk score. Key contributors include a peak acceleration magnitude median of 1.44 G (just above the PD-associated threshold of ≤ 1.44 G, suggesting reduced movement vigor), an RMS magnitude standard deviation mean of 0.032 G (slightly above the PD threshold of ≤ 0.03 G, indicating subtle motor variability), and REM duration standard deviation of 22.77 min (below the PD threshold of ≤ 35.99 min, reflecting altered sleep stability). Median REM duration of 21.5 min (below the PD threshold of ≤ 69.06 min) and cadence standard deviation of 14.84 steps/min (marginally below the PD threshold of ≤ 15.47 steps/min, hinting at potential gait instability) further support the risk profile. Prodromal markers include hyposmia (present) and a family history of Parkinson's disease, both of which independently increase risk, while other markers such as RBD screening and cognitive deficits were absent.

Figure 18 AI generated summary of PD risk report

The report then includes the overall PD risk score and a break-down in two individual risk scores:

1. The overall PD risk is a weighted average of the sleep and activity metrics-based PD risk score and of the prodromal PD risk score based on the MDS model (see Figure

- 19)**: The overall PD risk score of the previous reporting period and the cut-off and interquartile range (IQR) associated with PD are also presented.
2. The sleep and activity metrics-based PD risk score (SAM-PD risk score) derived from smartwatch data collected via mAI-Health (see **Figure 20**): The score is based on the SAM-PD risk model developed by AI-PROGNOSIS and reported in deliverable D3.4 'Final report on predictive modelling for PD'. The score is accompanied by the top-5 predictors and explainability evidence, which is essentially the local interpretable model-agnostic explanation (LIME) output for the particular SAM-PD risk score prediction presented in an easy-to-understand form for physicians. This includes a short description of the predictor in lay language, the predictor value, the range associated with PD, and the way it influences the SAM-PD risk score. The SAM-PD risk score of the previous reporting period and the cut-off and interquartile range (IQR) associated with PD are also presented.
 3. A prodromal PD risk score based on the risk and prodromal markers established by the MDS (Heinzel et al., 2019), reported by the patient via mAI-Health and/or logged by the attending physicians via mAI-Insights (see **Figure 21**): All markers are listed along with their likelihood ratios, the status reported by the patient via mAI-Health, the status indicated by the physician, and whether they were used in the prodromal PD risk calculation. The prodromal PD risk score of the previous reporting period and the MDS-defined cut-off for high risk are also presented.

Figure 19 Overall PD risk score in PD risk report

Figure 20 Sleep and activity metrics-based PD risk score in PD risk report

Figure 21 Prodomal PD risk score in PD risk report

Disclaimer

The Sleep and Activity metrics-based Parkinson's disease (PD) risk score (SAM-PD risk score) is a probability of having Parkinson's disease (PD) estimated by a machine learning model that has been trained to classify individuals as having PD or not based on sleep and activity metrics derived from daily acceleration data captured using a wrist-worn smartwatch, adjusted for age, sex, height, and weight. The model has been trained with data from 152 individuals with PD [68.8 (8.0) years average (std) age, 40% females, 6.1 (2.4) years average (std) disease onset] and 32 unaffected individuals [66.7 (12.6) years average (std) age, 41% females]. It has 0.90 balanced accuracy, 0.89 sensitivity and 0.90 specificity in detecting PD cases. The model performs best for individuals 55 to 74 years old, regardless of biological sex, with a body-mass index of 25.0-29.9 kg/m². The SAM-PD risk score exhibits excellent test-retest reliability when estimated with input sleep and activity metrics aggregated over 1 month or longer.

- 1 Weights have been determined using grid search for maximizing the binary classification performance of the overall Parkinson's disease risk score in detecting individuals with dopaminergic deficit (abnormal minimum putamen specific binding ratio measured with DaTSCAN) in a group of 141 individuals [65.3 (7.2) years average (std) age, 65% females] at risk of PD [having REM sleep behavior disorder, hyposmia or a genetic risk variation (SNCA, LRRK2, GBA)].
- 2 Model version 1.11
- 3 Heinzel, S., Berg, D., Gasser, T., Chen, H., Yao, C., Postuma, R. B., & Disease, the M. T. F. on the D. of P. (2019). Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*, 34(10), 1464-1470. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.27802>

Figure 22 Disclaimer and footer in PD risk report

Aligned with the AI-PROGNOSIS approach to Trustworthy AI, the report also includes a disclaimer that provides a short description of the population that generated the dataset used to train the SAM-PD risk model, key performance metrics and limitations. The footer of the report also includes the SAM-PD risk model version that output the SAM-PD risk score included in the report for auditing purposes (see **Figure 22**).

3.3.3 PD management

The 'Insights' section, when accessed from the details page of a patient with PD, is the space where the attending physician can initiate a new consultation, see data from previous consultations and access AI-PROGNOSIS-generated digital biomarkers and prognostic outputs. This section provides access to four areas (see **Figure 23**):

- Clinical consultation data, where HCPs can input and review detailed clinical assessments from each patient visit
- Reports on progression prediction based on clinical data and sleep and activity metrics derived from smartwatch data collected via mAI-Care
- Digital insights (digital biomarkers) derived from smartwatch data collected via mAI-Care
- Medication assistant reports: reports generated by the AIMED module for a specific medication regimen

Figure 23 'Insights' area for a specific patient with PD in mAI-Insights

3.3.3.1 Clinical consultations

By launching a new consultation, physicians can input and view clinico-demographic data including standardised clinical assessment scores, such as MDS-UPDRS Part III, and genetic analysis products, such as a Polygenic Risk Score (see **Figure 24** and Appendix – mAI-Insights screens). The system maintains a complete historical record, allowing HCPs to review and edit data from previous consultations.

New clinical consultation

Figure 24 New clinical consultation for a patient with PD in mAI-Insights

3.3.3.2 Progression reports

The Progression reports area provides access to the automatically-generated reports on PD progression prediction powered by the AI-PROGNOSIS progression prediction model (see Section 2.3.12.2 in D4.3). This report is currently being co-designed with Healthcare Professionals and will be presented in the refined MVP.

3.3.3.3 Digital insights

The digital insights section provides HPCs with digital biomarker data captured via mAI-Care.

The insights are organized into two main categories, motor fluctuations and physical activity.

Within motor fluctuations, HPCs can access several digital biomarker data (in the form of charts) associated with motor symptoms and medication side effects including:

- Slowness of hand movement (see **Figure 25**), derived from smartwatch data
- Slowness of finger movement, derived from touchscreen typing data collected via the Research Keyboard.
- Dyskinesia, derived from smartwatch data
- Rest tremor amplitude and constancy derived from smartwatch data.

These digital biomarkers are detailed in deliverable D3.3.

Figure 25 Slowness of hand movement chart

The physical activity area displays data related to physical activity and derived from smartwatch data including:

- Step count
- Activity intensity levels (sedentary, light, and moderate-vigorous) (see **Figure 26**)

Figure 26 Physical activity intensity levels graph

Each digital biomarker chart offers flexible viewing options including longitudinal tracking across weekly, monthly, 6-month, and yearly intervals, as well as average-intraday profiles over a selected period, where applicable. Charts are accompanied by an ‘About this chart’ section that provides additional details on the digital biomarker, its measurement method and the population that generated the data used for its development.

3.3.3.4 Medication assistant

The Medication assistant, the user-friendly title of the AI-PROGNOSIS AIMED support module, provides physicians with an AI-powered tool to optimise PD medication regimens and predict potential adverse outcomes. These reports can be saved and previewed from the ‘Insights’ table (see **Figure 27** and Appendix – mAI-Insights screens).

Figure 27 Medication assistant report list and medication assistant access point in mAI-Insights

HCPs can input a medication regimen, including medication type, dosage (in mg), and frequency of administration. The Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (LEDD) for the medication regimen is then automatically calculated (see Section 2.3.12.3 in D4.3) (see **Figure 28**).

Clinical data summary

PD medication breakdown:

Medication	Class	Frequency	Dosage (mg)	LEDD (mg)	Actions
Levodopa	Levodopa	1x daily	100	100	Remove
Cabergoline	Other	1x daily	5	400	Remove
Total LEDD				500 mg	

+ Add medication

Figure 28 Medication regimen table in PD medication assistant

Once medications are entered, the physician can generate risk predictions for three key adverse outcomes: dyskinesia, hallucinations and daytime sleepiness. The interactive interface allows clinicians to adjust medication dosages using intuitive sliders and immediately observe how these changes impact predicted risk levels, with all calculations performed live by the PD medication response predictive model. For each adverse outcome, the system presents a detailed analysis showing the top predictive factors through an interactive pie chart visualization that displays the relative impact of each predictor, allowing clinicians to understand which factors contribute most significantly to the predicted risk (see **Figure 29**).

Figure 29 Side-effect risk estimation explanation in Medication assistant.

The physician can choose to save the report for a specific medication regimen. The physicians have access to the saved reports in the Medication assistant area. All reports include model version information and timestamps, creating a documented history of medication optimization decisions that can be referenced for ongoing patient management and treatment adjustments.

4 Component level

Most of the components identified during the technical specification of the ecosystem have been implemented, either fully or partially. **Table 4** lists the components that have been integrated into at least one of the MVPs.

Table 4 List of components of the mAI digital health ecosystem applications MVPs

Component ID	Component name	mAI-Health	mAI-Care
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism	✓	✓
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker	✓	✓
COMP-LDB	Smartphone local database	✓	✓
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard		✓
COMP-ACT	Active cognition capturing (cognitive) tests		✓
COMP-PAMT	Comprehensive motor function assessment test		✓
COMP-SRQ	Self-reporting assessments	✓	✓
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager	✓	✓
COMP-VIS	Data visualisations		✓

4.1 Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism (COMP-SSM)

The smartwatch synchronisation mechanism is a component that facilitates the pairing of the smartwatch with the smartphone, as well as the collection of the raw data from the smartwatch to the application. The collected raw data include 3-axis accelerometer data, beat-to-beat intervals (BBI), and heart rate. While much of the functionality is implemented natively, certain features are exposed to the React Native layer to support user interaction, for example, initiating smartwatch pairing.

Using Garmin's Health SDK, which is packaged in an Android Archive (AAR) library, users pair the Garmin vivoactive 5 smartwatch with their smartphone. In order for the SDK to start providing the desired raw data, the logging of data needs to be enabled on the smartwatch. Once this is done, the SDK syncs with the smartwatch, and the data are ready to be retrieved by the data collection worker (see Section 4.2).

4.2 Data collection worker (COMP-WOR)

The data collection worker is a component that collects data from the smartwatch, saves them in the local database and then sends them to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases. It is implemented completely on the native side of the application, since it heavily interacts with Garmin's Health SDK.

For the worker to start, users must explicitly activate it. Once activated, it runs approximately every 30 minutes, depending on the device's battery level and the operating system's resource management. No further action is required from the users, as users, since the component runs in the background. Each time the process begins, users receive a silent push notification.

Upon initiation, the worker retrieves accelerometer, BBI and heart rate data from the smartwatch. During its first run, the collection retrieves data from the past two days, gathering any data recorded during this period. The last timestamp of the received data is saved, and for subsequent runs, this saved timestamp serves as the starting point to minimize collection time and avoid data duplication. If the last timestamp is more than two days old, it is replaced with the timestamp corresponding to exactly two days ago. This is because the smartwatch cannot store unlimited data and deletes older records in its memory.

Once the data fetching is complete, the data are stored in their corresponding tables in the local SQLite database, and the worker's second task begins: dispatching the data to the

backend. The worker queries the database tables and sends the resulting data to the backend via a secure API call. This call is secure, as a unique access token is requested at the beginning, and users are authenticated before proceeding. When the backend responds with an appropriate status code, indicating that the data were successfully saved in the AI-PROGNOSIS databases, the worker deletes the sent data and continues with the remaining data in the table. If the table is empty, it moves to the next one, repeating this process until all tables are empty. After completing its tasks, the worker is triggered again in about 30 minutes.

A prerequisite for the worker to fetch data from the smartwatch is that the SDK has established a Bluetooth connection with the smartwatch. To send the data to the backend system, a connection to the Internet via Wi-Fi is required.

If an error occurs during data transmission, the data is retained and will be retried during the next worker run. If the error is authentication-related, the worker attempts to refresh the access token. If the refresh succeeds, dispatching resumes and if it fails, the dispatch process is aborted. For other error types, the worker continues by sending the next data batch.

The data collection worker can be stopped by unpairing the smartwatch, disabling it through the app's settings, or logging out of the app.

4.3 Smartphone local database (COMP-LDB)

All data collected from the smartwatch, active cognitive tests, motor tests and self-reporting assessments, as well as application monitoring and error logs, are saved in a local SQLite database on the smartphone. For the application to use the least device storage possible, the data are stored only until they are sent to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases; once they have been successfully dispatched, they are deleted from the local storage.

The database is fully implemented on the native side of the app, since most data transactions occur while the data collection worker is running.

4.4 Research keyboard (COMP-CVK)

The Research keyboard is a custom Android smartphone keyboard developed by project partner AUTH and distributed as an AAR library. It passively captures typing-related data, including key tap events and typing settings, in the background during routine typing. Every time a typing session is completed (defined from the time the keyboard appears in the foreground to the time it disappears again), the data are saved in a dedicated SQLite database from where the data collection worker retrieves them.

4.5 Active cognitive tests (COMP-ACT)

A set of three tests have been implemented to assess aspects of the user's cognitive function.

- **A memory test:** The N-back memory test assesses the memory skills of the users. Users are presented with a stimulus and is then asked to remember if it matches the stimulus from the previous step (see **Figure 30**). There are 50 rounds and, in each round, the reaction time of the users, as well as whether the choice of the stimulus was correct are logged.
- **A balloon test:** The Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART) is a computerised decision-making task that is used to assess risk-taking behaviour. In each round, users are presented with a balloon with a randomly assigned maximum pump limit between 2 and 50. Each pump represents one point and users have to decide whether they want to keep pumping it to earn more points, with the risk of popping it, or to safely collect

the earned points (see **Figure 31**). There are 20 rounds and, in each round, the maximum points of the balloon, the points collected and whether the balloon was popped are logged.

- **A reaction test:** The stop-signal task measures attention by challenging the users to press a specific button based on the direction of an arrow or abstain from doing so if a red cross appears. The delay that the red cross appears is adaptive to the reaction time of the users (see **Figure 32**). There are 200 rounds, split in four blocks of 50 rounds each, and in each round, the reaction time, whether the choice was correct, as well as the presence of the red cross and its delay time are logged.

This component is developed completely in React Native and the results at the end of each test are stored in the in-app SQLite database. No internet connection is required while the tests are being performed. Data are sent to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases during the execution of the data-collection worker.

Figure 30 Memory (N-back) test

Figure 31 BART test

Figure 32 Reaction (stop-signal) test

4.6 Comprehensive motor function assessment test (COMP-PAMT)

The comprehensive motor function assessment test consists of test that requires from the user to perform a sequence of movements to evaluate posture, balance, gait and leg agility (see deliverable D3.3). Participants are presented with a set of instructions (see **Figure 33**) and afterwards perform these movements in front of the smartphone's camera which is capturing a live video stream (see **Figure 34**).

Figure 33 Comprehensive motor function test instructions

Figure 34 Example of real-time pose tracking during comprehensive motor function test execution

Using Google’s open-source MediaPipe⁵ framework, the test detects the user’s pose and skeletal landmarks in real time directly on the device. To protect user privacy, no video is saved locally but only the extracted landmark timeseries are transmitted to the backend after their analysis. These 3-D landmarks correspond to key joints of the person’s body (such as shoulders, knees or nose).

4.7 Self-reporting assessments (COMP-SRQ)

Both applications include self-reporting assessments through questionnaires. Users answer a set of questions both upon first use of the application and at predefined intervals thereafter.

The initial questionnaire in mAI-Heath, requires users to answer questions concerning their lifestyle, family medical history and symptoms that could be associated with PD (see **Figure 35**). The users are then asked to provide an update every six months.

A similar procedure is implemented in mAI-Care, which includes a monthly questionnaire consisting of three parts (see **Figure 36**):

1. The RBD Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ).
2. The Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS).
3. Certain questions on the perceived condition of the participants.

Question 1/14

First degree relative with Parkinson's disease

Has any of your first-degree relatives (parent, sibling, or child) been diagnosed with Parkinson's disease?

Yes

No

Not sure

I prefer not to say

Next

Figure 35 A question of the questionnaire on PD risk and prodromal markers included in mAI-Heath

Have or have had a disease of the nervous system (e.g. stroke, head trauma, RLS, narcolepsy, depression, epilepsy, inflammatory disease of the brain)?

Yes

No

Please specify:

Previous

Next

Figure 36 A question of the RBDSQ questionnaire included in mAI-Care

Sleep problems

Select all problems you experienced last night (You can select more than one)

Insomnia

Restless legs

Nocturia

Waking up several times

Waking up early

Pain at night

Rigidity

Sleepwalking

Save

Figure 37 Sleep disturbance logger

As part of the self-reporting assessments, mAI-Care users are also able to log sleep disturbances that occurred during the previous night (see **Figure 37**). There is a specific list of symptoms from which the users can choose multiple entries and save them. Those sleep disturbances will be shared with their attending HCP through mAI-Insights. This is

⁵ MediaPipe: <https://developers.google.com/mediapipe>

complementary to the digital biomarkers of REM sleep behaviour disorder and daytime sleepiness AI-PRONGOSIS is developing.

4.8 Data visualisations (COMP-VIS)

Data visualisations for mAI-Care mobile application have been developed through which the users can see charts of digital biomarker data that are produced by containers in the data processing pipelines (see Section 2.3.12 in D4.3). The users can adjust the time resolution of the graphs (day, week, month and year), depending on the data's nature. Digital biomarkers currently visualised include measurements of:

- Slowness of hand and finger movement
- Rest tremor
- Dyskinesia (see **Figure 38**)
- Physical activity (see **Figure 39**)

Figure 38 Dyskinesia graph in mAI-Care

Figure 39 Physical activity graph in mAI-Care

4.9 Notification channel manager (COMP-NCM)

The notification channel manager is implemented as two sub-components:

- A sub-component in the React Native side where Expo notifications⁶ handles the notifications that are sent from the mAI backend (by automatically configuring and utilizing Firebase Cloud Messaging⁷).
- A sub-component on the native side to send local notifications related to the operation of the data collection worker.

There are five different types of notifications users can receive in mAI-Health and mAI-Care:

React Native side

1. Self-reporting assessment notifications.
2. Active tests notifications, which include the cognitive tests and the comprehensive motor function assessment test (mAI-Care only),

Native side

3. Data sync notifications (see **Figure 40**).
4. Bluetooth connection notifications (prompting users to enable Bluetooth when it is switched off) (see **Figure 41**).
5. Wi-Fi connection notifications (to connect to Wi-Fi to upload data in case of no recent Wi-Fi connection) (see **Figure 41**).

If the user has enabled receiving task reminders, they will be notified when tasks are available to be performed.

Figure 40 Data sync notification

Figure 41 Wi-Fi and Bluetooth notifications

The data collection worker notification appears regardless of whether the users have reminders enabled. This is because the worker uses a foreground service for which the Android operating system demands apps to show a notification each time they run⁸. The Bluetooth notification will appear once daily when the data collection worker starts and detects no Bluetooth connection. The same applies to the Wi-Fi connection. These notifications cannot be turned off.

5 Deployment specifications

This section details the complete deployment specifications for the AI-PROGNOSIS health application ecosystem, outlining the infrastructure, tooling, and processes required to build,

⁶ Expo notification: <https://docs.expo.dev/push-notifications/sending-notifications/>

⁷ Firebase Cloud Messaging: <https://firebase.google.com/docs/cloud-messaging>

⁸ Android foreground service: <https://developer.android.com/develop/background-work/services/foreground-services?authuser=2>

deploy, operate, and monitor the application. This includes also the deployed data pipelines that support the project.

5.1 Infrastructure

A detailed view of the project's infrastructure was described in D4.3 and the next steps are based on it. All the project's data are stored in a highly available PostgreSQL database deployed on top of a Kubernetes cluster.

The availability of this data directly enables the project's next phases, which involve scheduled and interdependent tasks. These tasks are formally structured as data (processing) pipelines and need not only resource orchestration, but also a workflow orchestrator.

5.2 Apache Airflow

To facilitate this need, a dedicated workflow orchestration layer is introduced. Apache Airflow has been selected as the workflow orchestrator for its ability to model and manage these complex data flows.

5.2.1 Deployment

Apache Airflow is deployed on top of the Kubernetes cluster. This deployment follows a GitOps approach with the source of truth being the manifests residing in the project's GitHub repository (see **Figure 42**).

A screenshot of a GitHub web interface showing a YAML manifest file for Apache Airflow. The browser address bar shows the URL: https://github.com/AI-PROGNOSIS/manifests/blob/main/argocd/base/apps/airflow-app.yaml. The file content is as follows:

```
1  apiVersion: argoproj.io/v1alpha1
2  kind: Application
3  metadata:
4    name: airflow
5    namespace: argocd
6  spec:
7    project: default
8    source:
9      repoURL: https://airflow.apache.org
10     chart: airflow
11     targetRevision: 1.16.0
12     helm:
13     values: |
```

Figure 42 Airflow manifest hosted on GitHub

All management of the Airflow deployment lifecycle, including initial setup, upgrades, and configuration changes, is executed via Argo CD (see **Figure 43**), the GitOps continuous delivery tool of choice.

Figure 43 Airflow deployment through ArgoCD

5.2.2 Web user interface

With the deployment managed by ArgoCD, the Airflow webserver component provides a centralised, web-based user interface that acts as the primary interface for data pipeline monitoring, management and troubleshooting (see Figure 44).

Figure 44 Home screen of Airflow user interface

5.2.3 Pipelines

Airflow defines pipelines as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG). A DAG is a collection of all the tasks, organized in a certain way that reflects their relationship and execution order. This way, dependencies between tasks are easily handled (see **Figure 45**).

Figure 45 Overview of a Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG)

The actual Python code defining the DAGs resides in a separate, dedicated GitHub repository (see **Figure 46**).

Figure 46 Airflow Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG) hosted on separate repository

5.2.4 Execution

To achieve scalability, resource/dependency isolation, and consistent environments for all task execution, the Airflow deployment utilizes the Kubernetes Executor/Pod Operator. This way, whenever an Airflow task is ready to run, a dedicated Kubernetes pod is provisioned for that single task. Once the task is completed, the pod is terminated releasing the resources.

Tasks are defined as Docker images hosted on the project’s private image registry, Harbor (see **Figure 47**).

Figure 47 Docker images for data pipelines

Kubernetes Executor is configured to pull these task-specific images from Harbor, ensuring that only trusted and versioned images are used for data processing. This setup guarantees that the data pipelines are decoupled from the core Airflow infrastructure, making them inherently more resilient, easier to debug, and simpler to manage via version control.

5.2.5 Monitoring

Since the separate tasks run as separate Kubernetes pods the existing infrastructure enables monitoring. Prometheus, Grafana, and AlertManager provide robust infrastructure monitoring for the Airflow pods and the underlying Kubernetes cluster. Nevertheless, specific data workflow context is needed.

The Airflow deployment is configured to enable StatsD metrics. With this configuration, Airflow automatically emits a rich set of metrics on every component like the scheduler, webserver, and individual task instances. To make these metrics available for Prometheus scraping, an essential intermediary is deployed in the Kubernetes cluster: the StatsD exporter.

This component serves two main functions:

- Reception of metrics: Acts as a standard StatsD server, listening to network traffic sent by Airflow's components.
- Protocol translation: Converts the received StatsD format metrics into the Prometheus format which is a text-based HTTP endpoint.

```
airflow_dag_processing_last_run_seconds_ago{dag_file="physical_activity_test"} 14.894286
# HELP airflow_dag_processing_processes Metric autogenerated by statsd_exporter.
# TYPE airflow_dag_processing_processes counter
airflow_dag_processing_processes 718664
# HELP airflow_dag_processing_processor_timeouts Metric autogenerated by statsd_exporter.
# TYPE airflow_dag_processing_processor_timeouts counter
airflow_dag_processing_processor_timeouts 29
# HELP airflow_dag_processing_total_parse_time Metric autogenerated by statsd_exporter.
# TYPE airflow_dag_processing_total_parse_time gauge
airflow_dag_processing_total_parse_time 0.0014766380190849304
# HELP airflow_dag_processor_heartbeat Metric autogenerated by statsd_exporter.
# TYPE airflow_dag_processor_heartbeat counter
airflow_dag_processor_heartbeat{type="counter"} 1.458875e+06
```

Figure 48 Sample of metrics in text-based format

With the metrics stored in Prometheus, Grafana is leveraged to create dedicated airflow data dashboards.

5.2.6 Data versioning

This multi-layered architecture ensures that our data pipelines are versioned at every stage of their lifecycle. While the dedicated DAG repository maintains the versioning of the orchestration logic, Harbor, the private image registry, manages the versioning of the execution environment through immutable image tags. Within this ecosystem, OpenLineage a platform for collection and analysis of data lineage, acts as the vital metadata bridge. By explicitly exposing data versions and state from within our containerized tasks, it provides the link that connects specific code commits and image versions to their resulting data assets.

5.3 Data pipelines

The project utilises a list of data pipelines for specific purposes. Those correspond to the data processing pipelines that were described in D4.3 (see Section 2.3.12 in D4.3) and a comprehensive list is being presented below (see **Table 5**).

Table 5 List of AI-PROGNOSIS data pipelines

Partner responsible	Container ID	Container name	Included in MVP
AUTH	CONT-RISK	PD risk assessment	✓
AUTH	CONT-FSM	Fine upper limb slowness of movement assessment	✓
AUTH	CONT-GSM	Gross upper limb slowness of movement assessment	✓
AING	CONT-PROG	PD progression prediction	✓
KUL	CONT-MRP	PD medication response prediction	✓
KUL	COMP-RBD	RBD tracking	✓
KUL	COMP-DST	Daytime somnolence tracking	✓
CERTH	CONT-HARPA	Human activity recognition and physical activity tracking	✓
CERTH	CONT-RTT	Rest tremor tracking	✓
CERTH	CONT-DYT	Dyskinesia tracking	✓
CERTH	CONT-BPA	Balance / Posture assessment	
CERTH	CONT-ACA	Active cognitive function assessment	
CERTH	CONT-PCA	Passive cognitive assessment	Deprecated

These pipelines all share a similar flow. They begin by ingesting data, either from database tables or parquet files stored in the object storage (MinIO), and then, after performing the necessary transformations and computations, store the resulting output either in database tables or the object storage. Certain data pipelines though need to store intermediate results for later use, which they store in the object storage. A short description of the data pipelines included so far in the MVP is provided below. The data pipelines correspond to digital biomarkers and predictive models detailed in deliverable D3.3 and D3.4, respectively.

5.3.1 PD risk assessment

This pipeline operates in two stages. In the first stage, the raw accelerometer data are ingested via a parquet file. Various features are subsequently extracted, such as (1) sleep features, (2) physical activity features, (3) steps detected features, (4) wrist acceleration features and (5)

wear time. Except for the wrist acceleration features that run daily (see Section 5.3.2), these extractors run on a weekly schedule. In the second stage, a PD risk prediction score (SAM-PD score) is generated every six months, based on the full set of accumulated features.

5.3.2 Gross upper limb slowness of movement assessment

This pipeline also consists of multiple steps. First, the raw accelerometer data are ingested through a parquet file. Features are extracted and saved as intermediate data. These computations are performed daily. Then when the next step is run, the previously extracted features are used as input to compute the slowness of gross upper limb movement score. This calculation is performed daily.

5.3.3 Fine upper limb slowness of movement assessment

This pipeline consists of a single step. Typing session data from the database are ingested and the slowness of fine upper limb (finger) movement score is computed.

5.3.4 PD medication response prediction

This pipeline is the only one that users can directly interact with through the Medication Assistant in mAI-Insights. It is activated via an API call when users want to calculate the side effects probability based on certain medication regimens. The model also uses other clinical and demographic data captured through mAI-Care and mAI-Insights applications and stored in the database. The result is the probability of dyskinesia, hallucinations and daytime sleepiness, as well as explainability of these side effects.

5.3.5 RBD tracking

This pipeline consists of a single step. Raw accelerometer data are ingested daily through parquet files and the RBD features are extracted. The output persists through the database.

5.3.6 Daytime somnolence tracking

This pipeline also consists of a single step. Raw accelerometer data are ingested daily through parquet files, and the daytime somnolence features are extracted. The output persists through the database.

5.3.7 Human activity recognition and physical activity tracking

This pipeline consists of a single step. Raw accelerometer data are taken as input and the physical activity features are computed. The output persists through the database.

5.3.8 Rest tremor tracking

This pipeline consists of a single step. Raw accelerometer data are taken as input, and the rest tremor features are computed. Output persists through the database.

5.3.9 Dyskinesia tracking

This pipeline consists of a single step. Raw accelerometer data are taken as input, and the dyskinesia features are computed. Output persists through the database.

5.4 Local large language model explainer

We employed prompt engineering and an LLM to create easy-to-understand summaries explaining the outputs of the predictive models powering mAI-Insights. The local LLM explainer (also see corresponding Section in D4.3) is deployed as part of the PD risk assessment, PD progression prediction and PD medication response prediction pipelines. Its purpose is to generate a textual explanation of each prediction made by the Machine Learning (ML) model(s) included in the pipelines.

To generate an explanation, the following are provided as context in structured user prompt:

- a) SHAP⁹ values with the global explanation (overall ML model behaviour),
- b) LIME values (Ribeiro et al., 2016) with the local explanation of the top N features (explanation of the specific prediction), and
- c) relevant metadata, such as a feature glossary. This glossary provides a mapping for each feature along with a clear, plain-language description.

Using zero-shot prompting, the compiled prompt along with a system prompt with general guidelines is sent to the LLM with a request to generate an explanation based on the LIME values and the provided context. The final output is a textual explanation (summary) of the prediction in an appropriate language that is included in the associated clinician-facing reports of mAI-Insights. See Section 3.3.2.2 for a summary generated by the explainer based on the predictions of the PD risk assessment system included in the provide PD risk report sample.

The LLM employed is an open-source Qwen 8B¹⁰ model, quantized to 8-bit precision in the ‘.gguff’ format, downloaded from Hugging Face¹¹. The model is served locally via a llama.cpp server¹². A custom python library is used to extract the required global (SHAP) and local (LIME) explanations, compile the final user prompt and send the request to the local server. The Qwen 8B model was selected as the local LLM explainer in mAI-Insights because it offers an effective balance between performance, privacy, and computational efficiency. Its 8-bit quantized ‘.gguff’ format enables fast, on-premise execution, ensuring that sensitive PD data never leaves the secure environment. Moreover, Qwen 8B performs strongly in zero-shot summarization and reasoning tasks, making it well suited for transforming complex explanation artefacts, such as SHAP global importance values, LIME local feature contributions, and structured metadata, into clear, clinician-friendly narratives. PD prediction pipelines often involve heterogeneous inputs, and the model’s ability to integrate these into coherent, plain-language explanations enhances transparency and supports clinical decision-making. Finally, as an open-source model, Qwen 8B also provides full control over deployment, reproducibility, and versioning, avoiding reliance on external APIs and enabling domain-specific prompt engineering tailored to PD terminology. This flexibility strengthens trustworthiness and auditability, both of which are essential for explainable AI in healthcare. By generating concise, context-aware summaries of each prediction, the Qwen-based explainer directly contributes to the usability and interpretability of the PD risk assessment, progression prediction, and medication-response pipelines within mAI-Insights.

6 GDPR compliance

The AI-PROGNOSIS project processes personal data in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679 and applicable national data protection laws. Consortium partners have entered into a Joint Controller Data Processing Agreement in accordance with Article 26 GDPR, which defines roles, responsibilities and obligations for the joint processing of personal data. All processing activities are documented, periodically reviewed and supported by Data Protection Impact Assessments where required, in line with Articles 26–28 and 35 GDPR.

⁹ SHAP: <https://shap.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

¹⁰ Qwen 8B model: <https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen3-8B>

¹¹ Hugging Face: <https://huggingface.co>

¹² Llama.cpp server: <https://github.com/ggml-org/llama.cpp>

6.1 Lawfulness, purpose limitation and data minimisation

Personal data are processed lawfully, fairly and transparently on the basis of freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous consent (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR). Special categories of personal data, including health, genetic and biometric data, are processed on the basis of explicit consent and/or for scientific research purposes under Article 9 GDPR, subject to appropriate safeguards. Data collection and processing are limited to specified, explicit and legitimate research purposes and to what is necessary for achieving the project's scientific objectives.

6.2 Data storage, retention and security measures

Personal data are retained only for as long as necessary to fulfil the objectives of the project. Data are stored securely on certified cloud infrastructure and protected local systems operated by the consortium partners. Identifiable data remain exclusively under the control of the clinical partners and are not shared externally, while shared datasets are pseudonymised or anonymised where possible. Appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place to ensure data security and confidentiality, including restricted access controls, encrypted data transfers and secure storage environments. Furthermore, the transfer of the personal data collected using the AI-PROGNOSIS framework to the AI-PROGNOSIS data management infrastructure is performed with the implementation of encryption.

6.3 Data subject rights and transparency

Data subjects retain full control over their personal data and may exercise all rights under Chapter III of the GDPR, including the rights of access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, data portability, objection, and withdrawal of consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of prior processing. In the current study implementation, data subjects can exercise their rights by contacting their respective clinical site, which coordinates with the cloud administrators to ensure the appropriate actions are taken, including the secure deletion of personal data where applicable.

During the evaluation phase, the AI-PROGNOSIS application is accompanied by a comprehensive privacy policy that provides end users with all relevant information concerning the processing of their personal data. End users are duly informed about the scope and purpose of the processing activities, the categories of personal data collected and processed, and the specific processing operations performed. In addition, they are informed of their data protection rights and the procedures available for exercising those rights.

While the latter is also considered part of the routine user support services, end users may also submit requests directly to the project's authorised legal partner via a designated email address. Where direct submission is not feasible, requests may alternatively be lodged using a dedicated application form at the clinical site where the end user is located. In such cases, the responsible clinical partner shall forward the request to the authorised legal partner for further assessment and implementation.

7 Trustworthy AI considerations

The key features and qualities of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in accordance with the Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework of the project defined in D2.6 'Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (updated version)' are summarised below:

- Disclaimer on model input, training data (bias), expected performance, and limitations included in the clinician-facing reports of mAI-Insights
- Tailored UI elements and textual summary-generation mechanisms to facilitate the understanding of explainability evidence of model predictions included in mAI-Insights reports, supporting processing on-premise, ensuring that no personal or health data are transferred to external servers or third-party providers.
- Model versioning and output logging; version inclusion in clinician-facing reports to facilitate auditing
- UI/UX based on universal design principles and industry practices, informed by co-creation sessions
- mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps are supported by >80% of Android device base by late 2025¹³
- In-app educational content to facilitate understanding of the purpose of the technology
- GDPR compliance and privacy by design of the system

Trustworthy AI considerations regarding the development and evaluation of the underlying AI models are provided in the deliverable D3.4 'Final report on predictive modelling for PD'.

8 Accessing the applications

Two versions of the AI-PRONGOSIS applications exist, the MVP version and the version used in the AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies. The latter are modified versions of the MVPs to serve the scientific needs of the studies. Participants in the studies will be exposed to the MVP version during the user acceptance evaluation phase. To access either version of the AI-PROGNOSIS application for demo purposes, follow the below instructions.

8.1 MVP versions

The MVP versions of the mAI-Health and mAI-Care mobile applications can be accessed by downloading and installing the APK files:

- [APK for mAI-Health \(MVP version\)](#).
- [APK for mAI-Care \(MVP version\)](#).

Notes:

- *Only one* of the above applications can be installed on a single Android device at a time.
- APK installation requires the Install unknown apps permission to be enabled for the download/opening application (e.g., Chrome or a file manager (for instance)).

The mAI-Insights (MVP version) web application can be accessed by visiting:

<https://mai-insights.aiprognosis.squaredev.io/>

To log into the applications, use the credentials provided in Section 8.3.

8.2 Study versions

The study versions of the mobile applications can be accessed by downloading and installing through the Google Play store:

¹³ Android version market share: <https://gs.statcounter.com/android-version-market-share>

- Google Play Store entry for [mAI-Health](#).
- Google Play Store entry for [mAI-Care](#).

Notes:

- *Only one* of the above applications can be installed on a single Android device at a time.
- Both mobile apps are only available in Germany, France, Spain, the United Kingdom, Greece, and Belgium.

The mAI-Insights (study version) web application can be accessed by visiting:

<https://mai-insights.ai-prognosis.eu/>

To log into the applications, use the credentials provided in Section 8.3.

8.3 Credentials

Test users have been created that allow access to each of the AI-PROGNOSIS applications. The same credentials can be used to log into both the MVP and study versions.

- **mAI-Health**
Username: review-mai-health
Password: vdefLkHtLnYk
- **mAI-Care**
Username: review-mai-care
Password: KYE0OsMn8ZD7
- **mAI-Insights**
Username: review-mai-insights
Password: RrlyDwnegu2h

9 Conclusions and future developments

D4.4 delivers the MVP version of the mAI-Health, mAI-Care and mAI-Insights applications forming the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem for supporting PD screening and care. The MVPs implement most of the functional and non-function requirements (D4.3) and allow the proof-of-concept validation of the underlying predictive models in the AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies of the project. Alongside clinician-facing reports and digital biomarker visualisations, certain other product features that are novel or demand careful consideration, yet are not essential for the initiation of the AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies, are work in progress and are being/will be subjected to additional co-design sessions with the patient panel, clinicians, and technical partners. Those include:

- Option to log troublesome events in mAI-Care, specifically related with activities of daily living that are affected by PD and users want to keep track of.
- Additional digital insights in mAI-Insights, including sleep-related indicators, such as RBD presence and daytime somnolence, and motor function/cognitive test results.
- Option to dispute model predictions and flag cases.

- Other feedback features, including successful data upload confirmation messages and extensive details on data sync status

Moreover, certain data processing pipelines are being refined and have not yet been fully integrated with the rest of the AI-PROGNOSIS infrastructure (as indicated in **Table 5**). Adversarial testing will be applied once full integration is achieved, to assess robustness and uncover vulnerabilities when models are exposed to challenging or perturbed inputs.

Once MVPs are complete, they will be further subjected to hands-on experience workshops with the patient panel and clinicians. These workshops alongside the usability evaluation of the tools that is part of the AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies will generate user feedback that will be incorporated in the refined MVPs. The refined MVPs, powered a fully deployed and integrated backend, will be delivered with D4.5 'The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (refined MVP)'.

References

- Heinzel, S., Berg, D., Gasser, T., Chen, H., Yao, C., Postuma, R. B., & MDS Task Force on the Definition of Parkinson's Disease. (2019). Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*, 34(10), 1464-1470.
- Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., & Guestrin, C. (2016, August). "Why should i trust you?" Explaining the predictions of any classifier. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining* (pp. 1135-1144).

Appendix – mAI-Insights screens

New consultation for persons without PD monitored for risk

New clinical consultation

Review and update the status of each prodromal marker for the patient.

Risk/prodromal marker	LR+	LR-	Review by HCP	Reported by patient via mAI-Health
Male sex	1.2	0.8	Select status	Female
Regular pesticide exposure	1.5	NA	Select status	No
Occupational solvent exposure	1.5	NA	Select status	-
Non-use of caffeine	1.35	0.88	Select status	No
Former smoker	NA	0.91	Select status	Yes
Never smoker	1.2	NA	Select status	No
Current smoker	NA	0.51	Select status	No
First-degree relative with PD	2.5	NA	Select status	Yes
Known gene mutation (LRRK)		NA	Select status	-
Polygenic risk score	1.57	0.45	Select status	High
Substantia nigra hyperechogenicity	3.4	0.38	Select status	-
Diabetes mellitus (type II)	1.5	0.97	Select status	No
Physical inactivity	1.3	0.91	Select status	-
Low plasma urate levels	1.8	0.88	NA	-
PSG-proven RBD	130	0.65	Select status	No
Possible RBD (questionnaire)	2.8	0.89	Select status	No
Dopaminergic PET/SPECT clearly abnormal	43.3	0.66	Select status	-
Subthreshold parkinsonism	9.6	0.55	Select status	-
Abnormal quantitative motor testing	3.5	0.6	Select status	-
Olfactory loss	6.4	0.4	Select status	Yes
Constipation	2.5	0.82	Select status	No
Excessive daytime somnolence	2.7	0.86	Select status	Yes
Orthostatic hypotension (neurogenic)	18.5	0.88	Select status	-
Orthostatic hypotension (symptomatic)	3.2	0.8	Select status	No
Erectile dysfunction	3.4	0.87	NA	-
Urinary dysfunction	2	0.9	Select status	No
Depression	1.6	0.88	Select status	No
Global cognitive deficit	1.8	0.88	Select status	-

Cancel Save changes

New consultation for persons with PD

New clinical consultation

Assessment date			
Date of completion *	<input type="text" value="dd/mm/yyyy"/>		
Demographics			
Age at PD diagnosis *	<input type="text"/>		
Years of formal education	<input type="text"/>		
Biological sex *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>		
Genetics			
Polygenic Risk Score	<input type="text"/>		
Clinical			
Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose (mg/day) *	<input type="text"/>	MDS-UPDRS Part II total *	<input type="text"/>
MDS-UPDRS Part III total *	<input type="text"/>	Postural Instability & Gait Disorder *	<input type="text"/>
Tremor subscore *	<input type="text"/>	Rigidity subscore *	<input type="text"/>
Bradykinesia subscore *	<input type="text"/>	SCOPA-AUT total *	<input type="text"/>
REM Sleep Behavior Disorder *	<input type="text"/>	Epworth Sleepiness Scale *	<input type="text"/>
QUIP Score *	<input type="text"/>	BP lying (mmHg) *	<input type="text"/>
BP after 3 min standing (mmHg) *	<input type="text"/>	MDS-UPDRS Part I total *	<input type="text"/>
Pain item (UPDRS Part I) *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>	Fatigue item (UPDRS Part I) *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>
Apathy item (UPDRS Part I) *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>	Hallucinations/psychosis item *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>
Cognitive impairment item *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>	Montreal Cognitive Assessment total *	<input type="text"/>
MDS-UPDRS Part IV total *	<input type="text"/>	Hoehn & Yahr stage (global PD severity) *	<input type="text" value="Select..."/>

PD risk report

Name

Sarah Mitchell

Age	Sex	Date of birth	BMI	Date of report	Reporting period
68	F	30 / 4 / 1956	25.4	12 Jun 2025	Jan 2025 - Jun 2025

AI generated summary

The patient's overall Parkinson's Disease risk assessment for the period Jan 2025-Jun 2025 indicates a 75% probability of having Parkinson's, driven by a very high digital risk score. Key contributors include a peak acceleration magnitude median of 1.44 G (just above the PD-associated threshold of ≤ 1.44 G, suggesting reduced movement vigor), an RMS magnitude standard deviation mean of 0.032 G (slightly above the PD threshold of ≤ 0.03 G, indicating subtle motor variability), and REM duration standard deviation of 22.77 min (below the PD threshold of ≤ 35.99 min, reflecting altered sleep stability). Median REM duration of 21.5 min (below the PD threshold of ≤ 69.06 min) and cadence standard deviation of 14.84 steps/min (marginally below the PD threshold of ≤ 15.47 steps/min, hinting at potential gait instability) further support the risk profile. Prodromal markers include hyposmia (present) and a family history of Parkinson's disease, both of which independently increase risk, while other markers such as RBD screening and cognitive deficits were absent.

Overall Parkinson's disease risk score¹

Weighted average of the risk scores	Previous score	Cut-off and Interquartile Range (IQR) associated with PD
75%	Jun 2024 - Jan 2025 71%	Cut-off $\geq 51%$ IQR: 40%-61%

Sleep and activity metrics Parkinson's disease risk score²

Probability of having PD	Previous score	Cut-off and Interquartile Range (IQR) associated with PD
77%	Jun 2024 - Jan 2025 72%	Cut-off $\geq 67%$ IQR: 42%-62%

Top 5 predictors	Value	Reference range associated with PD	Lowers probability Increases probability
Peak Acceleration magnitude (Median)	1.44 G	≤ 1.44 G	
Median of peak acceleration measured at the wrist; reflects movement vigor, with lower values indicating possible slowness of movement.			
RMS Acceleration magnitude std. (Mean)	0.03 G	≤ 0.03 G	
Mean of standard deviations in root-mean-square acceleration magnitude across observation windows; captures average movement variability intensity.			
REM sleep duration (Standard deviation)	22.77 min	≤ 35.99 min	
Standard deviation of REM duration across nights; low variability may suggest altered or stereotyped sleep patterns.			
REM sleep duration (Median)	21.5 min	≤ 69.06 min	
Median duration of REM sleep across nights; shorter durations may suggest fragmented or disrupted sleep common in prodromal Parkinson's.			
Cadence (Standard deviation)	14.84 steps/min	≤ 15.47 steps/min	
Standard deviation of average cadence across walking bouts; low variability suggests uniform pace, while high variability may point to gait instability.			

Prodromal Parkinson's disease risk score³

Probability of having prodromal PD

7.8%

Previous score

Jun 2024 - Jan 2025

7%

Cut-off associated with prodromal PD

Cut-off \geq 80%

Risk/prodromal marker	LR+	LR-	Review by HCP	Reported by patient via mAI-Health	Included in risk calculation
Male sex	1.2	0.8	Confirmed	Female	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Regular pesticide exposure	1.5	NA	Suspected	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Occupational solvent exposure	1.5	NA	Unknown	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Non-use of caffeine	1.35	0.88	Confirmed	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Former smoker	NA	0.91	Confirmed	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
Never smoker	1.2	NA	Not present	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
Current smoker	NA	0.51	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
First-degree relative with PD	2.5	NA	Confirmed	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
Known gene mutation (LRRK)		NA	Not present	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Polygenic risk score	1.57	0.45	Confirmed	High	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Substantia nigra hyperechogenicity	3.4	0.38	Unknown	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Diabetes mellitus (type II)	1.5	0.97	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Physical inactivity	1.3	0.91	Unknown	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Low plasma urate levels	1.8	0.88	NA	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
PSG-proven RBD	130	0.65	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Possible RBD (questionnaire)	2.8	0.89	Not present	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dopaminergic PET/SPECT clearly abnormal	43.3	0.66	Unknown	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Subthreshold parkinsonism	9.6	0.55	Not present	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Abnormal quantitative motor testing	3.5	0.6	Unknown	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Olfactory loss	6.4	0.4	Confirmed	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Constipation	2.5	0.82	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Excessive daytime somnolence	2.7	0.86	Confirmed	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Orthostatic hypotension (neurogenic)	18.5	0.88	Not present	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Orthostatic hypotension (symptomatic)	3.2	0.8	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Erectile dysfunction	3.4	0.87	NA	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Urinary dysfunction	2	0.9	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Depression	1.6	0.88	Not present	No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Global cognitive deficit	1.8	0.88	Not present	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Disclaimer

The Sleep and Activity metrics-based Parkinson's disease (PD) risk score (SAM-PD risk score) is a probability of having Parkinson's disease (PD) estimated by a machine learning model that has been trained to classify individuals as having PD or not based on sleep and activity metrics derived from daily acceleration data captured using a wrist-worn smartwatch, adjusted for age, sex, height, and weight. The model has been trained with data from 152 individuals with PD [68.8 (8.0) years average (std) age, 40% females, 6.1 (2.4) years average (std) disease onset] and 32 unaffected individuals [66.7 (12.6) years average (std) age, 41% females]. It has 0.90 balanced accuracy, 0.89 sensitivity and 0.90 specificity in detecting PD cases. The model performs best for individuals 55 to 74 years old, regardless of biological sex, with a body-mass index of 25.0-29.9 kg/m². The SAM-PD risk score exhibits excellent test-retest reliability when estimated with input sleep and activity metrics aggregated over 1 month or longer.

- 1 Weights have been determined using grid search for maximizing the binary classification performance of the overall Parkinson's disease risk score in detecting individuals with dopaminergic deficit (abnormal minimum putamen specific binding ratio measured with DaTSCAN) in a group of 141 individuals [65.3 (7.2) years average (std) age, 65% females] at risk of PD [having REM sleep behavior disorder, hyposmia or a genetic risk variation (SNCA, LRRK2, GBA)].
- 2 Model version 1.11
- 3 Heinzel, S., Berg, D., Gasser, T., Chen, H., Yao, C., Postuma, R. B., & Disease, the M. T. F. on the D. of P. (2019). Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*, 34(10), 1464–1470. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.27802>

Medication assistant report

Medication assistant report

Report date: 19 December 2025
 Model version:

Name

John Doe

Age: 64 Sex: Male Date of birth: 15/03/1960

Patient ID: 10234

Disease duration: 3 years

Medication state: **ON (medication active)**

Genetic status: **Sporadic (no known PD-related mutations)**

Clinical data summary

PD medication breakdown:

Medication	Class	Frequency	Dosage (mg)	LEDD (mg)
Amantadine	Amantadine	2	100	200
Levodopa	Levodopa	1	200	200
Total LEDD				400 mg

Medication outcomes summary

Risk predictions

Model output

Key predictors impact analysis

Dyskinesia Hallucinations Daytime sleepiness

Predicted dyskinesia risk: 5.92%

